

MANAGEMENT OF TOMATO LEAF CURL VIRUS BY INSECT VECTOR (WHITEFLY) CONTROL WITH VARIOUS PEST MANAGEMENT COMPONENTS

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Abstract

The field experiment was conducted at Horticulture Research Scheme (Vegetable) VNMKV, Parbhani during Rabi, 2017-18 and Summer 2018-19 to find out the effect of different insecticides viz., imidacloprid, thiomethoxam, azadirachtin, chlorantraniliprole and pyriproxyfen for management of whitefly (vector of tomato leaf curl virus). The results showed that treatment T₁ (Imidacloprid seed treatment + spraying of Imidacloprid at 15 days interval from 30 days after emergence of crop) recorded lowest whitefly population i.e. 3.23 whitefly/ leaf in Rabi season, whereas it was 5.15 whitefly/leaf in Summer season. The disease incidence was also found less in this treatment i.e. 14.28 per cent and 23.81 per cent in Rabi and Summer season, respectively. The highest fruit yield during Rabi season (347.83 q/ha) with best ICBR (1:15.48) was observed in treatment T₁, while during Summer season the fruit yield in this treatment was 306.13 q/ha with best ICBR of 1:22.80.

Keywords: Leaf curl, Tomato, Whitefly, Imidacloprid.**Introduction**

Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) is one of the distinguished vegetable under Solanaceae family. It is one of the most popular vegetable crops grown all over the world. China leads in production and productivity of tomato followed by India United State of America, Turkey, Egypt and Iran. In India, the area, production and productivity was 789.2 thousand hectares, 19759.3 thousand metric tonnes and 25.0 MT respectively during 2017-18. In Maharashtra, the area, production and productivity was 45.50 thousand hectares, 1086.56 thousand metric tonnes and 23.88 metrics tonnes per hectares respectively during 2017-18 (Anonymous 2018). It is mostly grown in Pune, Nashik, Nagpur and Gadchiroli major producing district in Maharashtra. The most significant pathogenic diseases are those that are viral in nature. ToLCV is not spread by nematodes, seeds, soil, sap, or other external agents; rather, it is persistently and circulative transmitted by whiteflies (*Bemisia tabaci* Genn.) by grafting. ToLCV can be transferred from diseased tomato fruits to healthy plants by whiteflies (Delatte et al., 2003). Among the most deadly plant diseases in the world is the monopartite begomovirus ToLCV. A ToLCV infection can result in a 100% reduction in tomato yield. Tomato plants with the infection show slower growth, a significant decrease in leaf size, yellowing, chlorosis, and leaf curling of the young leaves. Because of its widespread occurrence and quick

spread to new places, it is a disease with significant economic impact on the entire world (Prasad et al.2020).

Seasonally, the incidence of ToLCV in Karnataka's tomato-growing regions varied between 17–100% (Saikia and Muniyappa, 1989). Since infection occurred within four weeks of transplanting in the field and yield loss exceeded ninety percent, this investigation was conducted to determine the value of botanicals, chemicals, and cultural practices in the integrated management of tomato leaf curl virus disease (Jones 2004).

Materials and methods**Management of insect vector**

To study the effect of different insecticides on whitefly population, disease incidence and yield of tomato, a field experiment was conducted on the research farm of the Horticulture Research Scheme (Vegetable), VNMKV, Parbhani during Rabi, 2017 and Summer, 2018.

Experimental details:

Design	:	R.B.D
Variety	:	Pusa Ruby
Replication	:	Three
Plot Size	:	3.0x3.15m ²
Spacing	:	60x45 cm
Treatment	:	Nine

Treatment details:

Sr. No.	Treat. No.	Treatment details
1	T ₁	Seed treatment with Imidacloprid 48 FS @ 5 g / kg + Spraying with Imidacloprid 17.8 SL @ 0.005%
2	T ₂	Seed treatment with Thiomethoxam 70 WS@ 5 g / kg + Spraying with Thiomethoxam 25 WG 0.01%
3	T ₃	Seed treatment with Imidacloprid 48 FS@ 5 g / kg + Spraying with Azadirachtin@ 5% (NSKE)
4	T ₄	Chlorantraniliprole 8.8%+Thiomethoxam17.5% SC (Soil drenching 50 to 100ml/plant, application after 8 to 10 days after transplanting.)
5	T ₅	Spraying with Imidacloprid 17.8 % SL @ 0.005%
6	T ₆	Spraying with Thiomethoxam 25 W. G. @ 0.01%
7	T ₇	Spraying with Pyriproxyfen 10% EC@0.01%
8	T ₈	Spraying with Azadirachtin@ 5% (NSKE)
9	T ₉	Control (Untreated)

Thirty days old seedling of tomato cv. Pusa Ruby (susceptible) was transplanted on 17/10/2017 and on 17/01/2018 in the experimental plots during Rabi2017 and Summer 2018, respectively. The crop was raised as per recommended package of practices and protective irrigation was given as and when required.

Insecticides and plant products were sprayed at 30, 45, 60 and 75 days after transplanting. Observations were recorded on whitefly

population and disease incidence on tomato. Whitefly count was recorded as per the method modified by Sipell *et al.* (1982). Whiteflies were counted early in the morning before 7.30 A.M. on top, middle and bottom leaves of randomly selected plants in each replicated treatment, from 7 to 90 days after transplanting at an interval of 7 days. The vector population before and after imposing treatments were recorded. The transformation of vector population

was done by using Poison formula $\sqrt{x} + 0.5$, where x is the average number of vectors and data so obtained was analyzed statistically.

Per cent disease incidence

The plants showing symptoms of tomato leaf curl disease were recorded from 15 to 90 days after transplanting with an interval of 15 days and disease incidence was calculated.

$$\text{Per cent disease incidence} = \frac{\text{Number of plants infected}}{\text{Total number of plants observed}} \times 100$$

Per cent disease control

$$\text{Per cent disease control} = \frac{(C - T)}{C} \times 100$$

Where,

C=percent disease incidence in control plot

T=percent disease incidence in treatment plot

Incremental Cost: Benefit ratio (ICBR)

To find out the most effective and economical treatment, the incremental cost benefit ratio (ICBR) was worked out. For this the expenditure incurred on inputs viz insecticides and labour charges on spraying were taken into account. Total monetary gain per treatment was worked out, based on the existing selling rates of the tomato in the market data.

Results and Discussion

Effect of insecticide on whitefly population dynamics in Rabi, 2017 and Summer, 2018.

To study the effect of different insecticides on whitefly population dynamics in Rabi and Summer, total 13 counts of whiteflies with an interval of 7 days were recorded. The data were statically analyzed and presented in Tables 1 and 2.

The results revealed that, T₁ (seed treatment with imidacloprid + spraying with imidacloprid), T₂ (seed treatment with thiomethoxam + spraying with thiamethoxam), T₄ (chlorantraniliprol + thiamethoxam soil drenching), T₃ (seed treatment with imidacloprid + Spraying with azadirachtin), spraying with insecticides viz., imidacloprid (T₅), thiamethoxam (T₆), pyriproxyfen (T₇) and spraying of azadirachtin (T₈) showed significant reduction in whitefly population in both Rabi and Summer. All the treatments differed in their efficacy. Minimum whitefly population was recorded during early growth stages, while it was increased with increase in the age of crop in both Rabi and Summer. It was observed that among all the treatments insecticides significantly decreased whitefly population in most of the count than other treatments. Amongst all the treatments, insecticides reduced whitefly population significantly as compared with T₉ (untreated control) in both Rabi and Summer.

In Rabi Table 1 revealed that seed treatment with imidacloprid + spraying with imidacloprid reduced whitefly population. Among all the treatments, insecticides reported less number of whitefly population as compared with the other treatment in all the 13 counts. Minimum whitefly population in most of the counts was observed in treatment T₁ (seed treatment with imidacloprid + spraying with imidacloprid) as compared with other treatment which was followed by T₂ (seed treatment with thiomethoxam + spraying with thiamethoxam). The treatments viz., T₇ (spraying of pyriproxyfen) and T₈ (spraying of azadirachtin) recorded maximum number of whitefly as against over T₉ (untreated control). However in Summer Table 19 similar trend was observed in few counts.

To study effect of spraying insecticide in Rabi and Summer average of 13 counts of whitefly population was worked out and data were analyzed the results on average population depicted in Table 1 and 2.

In Rabi season, the treatment T₁ (seed treatment with imidacloprid + spraying with imidacloprid) recorded significantly less whitefly population 1.34 whitefly / leaf than control 1.97 whitefly / leaf respectively. The second and third best treatment found were T₂ (seed treatment with thiomethoxam + spraying with thiamethoxam) and T₄ (chlorantraniliprol + thiamethoxam soil drenching) which recorded average whitefly population of 1.38 and 1.42 whitefly / leaf

respectively. This was followed by viz., T₃ (seed treatment with imidacloprid + spraying with azadirachtin) 1.44 whitefly/leaf, T₅ (spraying of imidacloprid); 1.45 whitefly / leaf, T₆ (spraying of thiamethoxam) 1.47 whitefly / leaf and T₇ (spraying of pyriproxyfen) 1.54 whitefly / leaf was at par with T₈ (spraying of azadirachtin) 1.60 whitefly/leaf. Among all the treatment, the treatment T₈ (spraying of azadirachtin) was found least effective and recorded average whitefly population as of 1.60 whitefly / leaf as against 1.97 whitefly / leaf average whitefly population per leaf in T₉ (untreated control).

In Summer season, the treatment T₁ (seed treatment with imidacloprid + spraying with imidacloprid) recorded significantly less whitefly population 2.14 whitefly / leaf than control 2.67 whitefly / leaf respectively. The second and third best treatment found were T₂ (seed treatment with thiomethoxam + spraying with thiamethoxam) and T₄ (chlorantraniliprol + thiamethoxam soil drenching) which recorded average whitefly population of 2.16 and 2.19 whitefly / leaf respectively. This was followed by viz., T₃ (seed treatment with imidacloprid + spraying with azadirachtin) 2.21 whitefly/leaf, T₅ (spraying of Imidacloprid) 2.23 whitefly / leaf, T₆ (spraying of thiamethoxam) 2.25 whitefly / leaf and T₇ (spraying of pyriproxyfen) 2.26 whitefly / leaf was at par with T₈ (spraying of azadirachtin) 2.32 whitefly/leaf. Among all the treatment, the treatment T₈(spraying of azadirachtin) was found least effective and recorded average whitefly population as of 2.32 whitefly / leaf as against 2.67 whitefly / leaf average whitefly population per leaf in T₉ (untreated control).

In both season (Rabi and Summer) the treatment T₁ (seed treatment with imidacloprid + spraying with imidacloprid) and T₂ (seed treatment with thiomethoxam + spraying with thiamethoxam), were found to be best reducing whitefly population as compared with the rest of the treatments which were followed by the treatment T₄ (chlorantraniliprol + thiamethoxam soil drenching) and T₃ (seed treatment with imidacloprid + spraying with azadirachtin) respectively.

Effect of spraying insecticide on disease incidence in Rabi, 2017 and

Summer, 2018

Effect of spraying insecticide on disease incidence of tomato leaf curl disease in tomato in Rabi and Summer at different growth and intervals was studied and results are presented in Table 3 and 4. The result Table 3 revealed that, the treatments T₁ (seed treatment with imidacloprid + spraying with imidacloprid), T₂ (seed treatment with thiomethoxam + spraying with thiamethoxam), T₄ (chlorantraniliprol+ thiamethoxam soil drenching), T₃ (seed treatment with imidacloprid + Spraying with azadirachtin), spraying with insecticides viz., imidacloprid (T₅), thiamethoxam (T₆), pyriproxyfen (T₇) and spraying of Azadirachtin (T₈) showed significant reduced disease incidence in both Rabi and Summer season. The data indicated that, the incidence of disease was delayed in all treatments up to 15 days in both Rabi and Summer season. Disease incidence increased significantly with increase in age of crop. In both season all the treatments were found more efficient in reducing the disease over control.

In Rabi Table 3 all the treatment and at all intervals from 15 to 90 days after transplanting T₁ (seed treatment with imidacloprid and spraying with imidacloprid) recorded least disease incidence followed by T₂ (seed treatment with thiomethoxam + spraying with thiamethoxam). Maximum disease incidence was observed in T₇ (spraying of pyriproxyfen) followed by T₈ (spraying of azadirachtin) as against over T₉ (untreated control). However in Summer Table 21 similar trend was observed in disease incidence.

Results from Table 3 and 4 on effect of spraying insecticide against the disease incidence in Rabi season revealed that, all the treatments significantly reduced the disease incidence over control. The mean leaf curl disease incidence recorded in all the treatment was ranged from 5.52 to 14.09 percent as against 15.04 percent in untreated control. However, amongst all the treatments T₁ (seed treatment with imidacloprid+ spraying with imidacloprid) recorded least mean

disease incidence (5.52%) and this was followed by T₂ (seed treatment with thiomethoxam + spraying with thiamethoxam) with mean disease incidence (7.00%). The treatment of soil drenching chlorantraniliprol+ thiamethoxam (T₃), seed treatment imidacloprid + spraying with azadirachtin (T₄), spraying of imidacloprid (T₅), spraying of thiamethoxam (T₆), spraying of pyriproxyfen (T₇) recorded the mean disease incidence i.e. 8.18, 9.51, 10.47, 11.61 and 12.75 per cent respectively. Maximum mean disease incidence was observed in treatment T₈ (spraying of azadirachtin) recorded the mean disease incidence 14.09 per cent as against in T₉ (untreated control) i.e.15.04 per cent.

In Summer season the mean leaf curl disease incidence recorded in all the treatment was ranged from 7.93 to 17.61 percent as against 26.70 percent in untreated control. However, amongst all the treatments T₁ (seed treatment with imidacloprid+ spraying with imidacloprid) recorded least mean disease incidence (7.93 %) and this was followed by T₂ (seed treatment with thiomethoxam + spraying with thiamethoxam) with mean disease incidence (9.71%). The treatment of soil drenching chlorantraniliprol+ thiamethoxam (T₃), seed treatment imidacloprid + spraying with azadirachtin (T₄), spraying of imidacloprid (T₅), spraying of thiamethoxam (T₆), spraying of pyriproxyfen (T₇) recorded the mean disease incidence i.e. 10.63, 11.26, 13.32, 14.60 and 16.18 per cent respectively. Maximum mean disease incidence was observed in treatment T₈ (spraying of azadirachtin) recorded the mean disease incidence 17.61 per cent as against in T₉ (untreated control) i.e. 20.79 per cent.

Thus, the data Table 3 and 4 indicated that the treatments viz; Imidacloprid seed treatment +its spraying (T₁) followed by thiomethoxam seed treatment + thiomethoxam spraying (T₂) and chlorantraniliprol+ thiomethoxam (T₃) were found most effective in checking the occurrence of insect vector whitefly as well as incidence of leaf curl disease in tomato cv. Pusa Ruby during *Rabi* and Summer season.

Results Table 3 obtained on the percent reduction of leaf curl disease incidence over untreated control in *Rabi* revealed that, the treatment T₁ (seed treatment with imidacloprid+ spraying with imidacloprid) reduced the disease incidence to maximum extent of 45.82 percent, which was significantly superior to all treatments. The second best treatment in reducing disease incidence was T₂ (seed treatment with thiomethoxam + spraying with thiamethoxam) 37.50 per cent which was followed by T₄ (chlorantraniliprol + thiamethoxam soil drenching) and T₃ (seed treatment with imidacloprid + Spraying with azadirachtin) recorded 33.34 and 24.98 per cent reduction, respectively. The treatment of spraying with insecticides viz., imidacloprid (T₅), thiamethoxam (T₆), pyriproxyfen (T₇) and spraying of azadirachtin (T₈) reduced the disease to an extent of 29.14, 20.83 ,12.47 and 4.15 per cent reduction respectively over T₉(untreated control).

Results Table 4 obtained on the percent reduction of leaf curl disease incidence over untreated control in Summer revealed that, the treatment T₁ (seed treatment with imidacloprid + spraying with imidacloprid) reduced the disease incidence to maximum extent of 66.67 percent, which was significant superior to all treatments. The second best treatment in reducing disease incidence was T₂ (seed treatment with thiomethoxam + spraying with thiamethoxam) percent which was followed by T₄ (chlorantraniliprol + thiamethoxam soil drenching) and T₃ (seed treatment with imidacloprid + Spraying with azadirachtin) which recorded 64.45 and 62.21 per cent reduction, respectively. The treatment of spraying with insecticides viz., imidacloprid (T₅), thiamethoxam (T₆), pyriproxyfen (T₇) and spraying of azadirachtin (T₈) reduced the disease to an extent of 46.67, 40.00, 33.34 and 26.67 per cent reduction respectively over T₉ (untreated control).

Effect of insecticide on yield

In *Rabi* season results Table 5 revealed that, insecticides sprayings increased significantly yield of tomato. Among all the insecticides sprayed, imidacloprid gave significantly highest fruit yield (347.83

q/ha) over unsprayed control (207.40 q/ha). However, significantly highest fruit yield (347.83 q/ha) was recorded with treatment T₁ (Imidacloprid seed treatment + spraying with imidacloprid) with significantly least average whitefly population (1.34/leaf) and leaf curl disease incidence (5.52 percent). The second and third best treatment found was T₂ (seed treatment with thiomethoxam + spraying with thiomethoxam) which recorded fruit yield (346.03 q/ha) and T₄ (chlorantraniliprol+ thiomethoxam soil drenching) (328.88 q/ha). This was followed by T₃ (seed treatment imidacloprid + spraying with azadirachtin) which gave fruit yield (256.82 q/ha). Spraying of insecticide, imidacloprid (T₅) and thiomethoxam (T₆) (254 q/ha and (247.61 q/ha) respectively. Spraying with pyriproxyfen (T₇) and azadirachtin (T₈) in fruit yield (235.66q/ha and 226.13 q/ha) respectively as against 207.40 q/ha fruit yield (T₉) untreated control. In Summer season, the fruit yield in all the treatments was ranged from (306.13 q/ha) over untreated control to (88.88 q/ha). However, significantly highest fruit yield (306.13 q/ha) was recorded with treatment T₁ (Imidacloprid seed treatment +spraying with imidacloprid) with significantly least average whitefly population (2.14/leaf) and leaf curl disease incidence (7.93 percent). The second and third best treatment found were T₂ (seed treatment with thiomethoxam + spraying with thiomethoxam) and T₄ (chlorantraniliprol + thiomethoxam soil drenching) which recorded fruit yield respectively of 260.63 and 287.30 q/ha. This was followed by the treatments T₃ (175.34 q/ha) T₅ (151.32 q/ha), T₆ (137.46q/ha) and T₇ (124.02 q/ha), T₈ (114.28 q /ha) respectively as against 88.88q/ha fruit yield untreated control (T₉).

Thus, the present results indicated that the population of whitefly and leaf curl disease incidence in tomato could effectively managed with the integration of the insecticides viz; seed treatment and spraying with imidacloprid and thiomethoxam which certainly gave economical yields in tomato.

Results of the present study obtained on the vector management of the tomato leaf curl virus disease in tomato with insecticide are in conformity with those reported earlier by several workers.(Butter and Rataul, 1973; Yassin *et al.*, 1975; Rubeinstein *et al.*, 1999; Palumbo *et al.*, 2001; Manson *et al.*, 2000; Naik 2002; Elbert and Nauen, 2004;Singh *et al.*,2004; Ali *et al.*, 2005; Salam, 2005; Ahemd, 2006; Rajasri *et al.*, 2009; Kodandaram *et al.*, 2010; Al-Kherb, 2011;El-sayed,2013; Barrania and Abou-Taleb, 2014; Singh and Prajapati,2014;Dhar and Bhattacharya 2015; Mourya *et al.* 2015; Dechan *et al.*,2017). Ahmed *et al.* (2001) evaluated the effect of imidacloprid on incidence of tomato yellow leaf curl virus by using two applications at four different rates (47.6, 71.4, 95.2, and 119 g a.i. /ha) under field conditions and found that the repeated rates of imidacloprid reduced disease incidence at all the dosage and the disease incidence was reduced to 2.2 to 17% and the treated plots consistently had higher yields than control plots. Palumbo *et al.* (2001) suggested that the imidacloprid and thiamethoxam are the most effective insecticide for the control of *B. tabaci*. Salam (2005) reported that mung bean crop can be protected by seed treatment with imidacloprid 70 WS (5 gm/kg) along with 2 sprays of imidacloprid 17.8 SL (0.24 ml/lit) at 45 and 60 days after planting recorded least number of whiteflies per plant and there was significant increase in all the growth and yield parameters assessed. El-sayed (2013) evaluated four insecticides and two commercial plant extracts for their efficiency against *Bemisia tabaci* on tomato plants Thiamethoxam (1.82 nymph / leaf) Imidacloprid gave a good reduction in the mean number of *B. tabaci*. Dechan *et al.* (2017) evaluated different chemicals to know their efficacy by controlling the vector *Bemisia tabaci* which is responsible for spread of the disease. The application of imidacloprid (seed treatment+ seedling dip+ foliar application) at 70 DAT was found most effective treatment in maintaining the disease intensity of 8.14 %. The other combinations of imidacloprid were also effective in reducing the disease intensity at different days after transplanting. The high efficacy of imidacloprid is exhibited due to its systemic insecticide

nature that translocate rapidly through plant tissues. Imidacloprid acts on several types of post-synaptic nicotinic acetylcholine receptors in the nervous system in insect, these receptors are located only within the central nervous system. Seed treatment of imidacloprid 5g/Kg of seed and thiomethoxam (5g/Kg) of seed effective only where whitefly is serious as early Season pest (40 - 60 Days only).

Incremental cost: benefit ratio (ICBR)

Results (Table 6 and 7) obtained on the economics of various spray treatments integrated for management of leaf curl disease revealed that all the treatments significantly reduced the insect vector whitefly population, leaf curl disease incidence and there by increased fruit yield over untreated control. All the treatments gave maximum additional income as well as net profit over untreated control in both Rabi and Summer season.

In Rabi season gross income recorded with all the treatments over unsprayed control was ranged from Rs.1043490/- to Rs.622200/- per ha. and corresponding net profit with all the treatment was ranged from Rs. 980190/- to Rs. 561750/- per ha. However, highest gross income (Rs.1043490/-) and highest net profit (Rs.980190/-) were recorded with treatment T₁. This was followed by treatments T₂, T₄, T₃, T₅, T₆, T₇ and T₈. Based on ICBR the most economical treatments found were T₁ and T₂ with ICBR 1:15.48 and 1:15.18 respectively both of which were on par. The second and third best treatments found were T₄ (ICBR: 1:12.81) and T₃ (ICBR: 1:11.32).

In Summer season gross income recorded with all the treatments over unsprayed control was ranged from Rs. 1530650/- to Rs. 444400/- per ha. and corresponding net profit with all the treatment was ranged from Rs. 1466350/- to Rs. 382650/- per ha. However, highest gross income (Rs.1530650/-) and highest net profit (Rs.1466350/-) were recorded with treatment T₁. This was followed by treatments T₂, T₄, T₃, T₅, T₆, T₇ and T₈. Based on ICBR the most economical treatments found were T₁ and T₂ with ICBR (1:22.80 and 1:19.00) respectively. The second and third best treatments found were T₄ (ICBR: 18.83) and T₃ (ICBR: 1:12.80). Rests of the treatments were also found economical for the management.

Thus, among all the treatments, a combination of seed treatment and spraying of insecticide gave significantly higher yield and were economical.

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Table 1. Effect of various treatment integration on vector *B. tabaci* population in tomato during Rabi, 2017-18 (Cv. Pusa Ruby)

Treat. No.	Treatments	Number of whiteflies /leaf* at DAT													
		7	14	21	28	35	42	49	56	63	70	77	84	91	Mean
T ₁	Seed treatment (ST) with Imidacloprid 48 FS @ 5 g / kg+ Spraying with (SP) Imidacloprid 17.8 SL @ 0.005%	0.00	0.00	1.23	1.21	1.68	1.24	1.51	1.30	1.47	1.44	1.51	1.60	1.99	1.34
T ₂	ST with Thiomethoxam 70 WS@ 5 g / kg +SP with Thiomethoxam 25 WG 0.01%	0.00	0.00	1.26	1.36	1.74	1.30	1.56	1.13	1.49	1.46	1.55	1.65	2.08	1.38
T ₃	ST with Imidacloprid 48 FS @ 5 g /kg+ SP with Azadirachtin@ 5% (NSKE)	0.00	0.70	1.21	1.41	1.7	1.24	1.53	1.31	1.46	1.43	1.52	1.62	2.19	1.44
T ₄	Chlorantraniliprol 8.8% + Thiomethoxam17.5% SC (Soil drenching 50 to 100ml/plant, application after 8 to 10 DAT.)	0.00	0.00	1.23	1.56	1.74	1.30	1.59	1.35	1.52	1.47	1.57	1.71	2.10	1.42
T ₅	Spraying with Imidacloprid 17.8 % SL@ 0.005%	0.00	1.09	1.21	1.33	1.72	1.01	1.52	1.32	1.48	1.42	1.53	1.63	2.25	1.45
T ₆	Spraying with Thiomethoxam 25 W. G. @ 0.01%	0.00	1.07	1.19	1.29	1.71	1.29	1.52	1.31	1.46	1.42	1.52	1.59	2.34	1.47
T ₇	Spraying with Pyriproxyfen 10% EC@0.01%	0.00	1.07	1.28	1.41	1.76	1.47	1.57	1.33	1.52	1.41	1.56	1.65	2.50	1.54
T ₈	Spraying with Azadirachtin@ 5% (NSKE)	0.00	1.07	1.29	1.53	1.77	1.41	1.59	1.37	1.49	1.48	1.57	1.67	2.98	1.60
T ₉	Control (Untreated)	0.00	1.14	1.57	1.66	1.77	1.82	1.86	1.99	2.13	2.18	2.19	2.35	2.99	1.97
	S.E. ±	0.00	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.06	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.02	0.70	
	C.D. at 5%	0.00	0.10	0.14	0.13	NS	0.19	0.12	0.17	0.14	0.15	0.09	0.08	2.12	

* Figures in parentheses are $\sqrt{x+0.5}$ transformed values. DAT= Days after transplanting. Mean of three replication

Table 2. Effect of various treatment integration on vector *B. tabaci* population in tomato during Summer, 2018-19 (Cv. Pusa Ruby).

Treat. No.	Treatments*	Number of whiteflies /leaf** at DAT													
		7	14	21	28	35	42	49	56	63	70	77	84	91	Mean
T ₁	Seed treatment (ST) with Imidacloprid 48 FS @ 5 g / kg+ Spraying with (SP) Imidacloprid 17.8 SL @ 0.005%	0.00	1.34	1.79	1.72	1.62	1.95	1.77	2.16	2.38	3.11	2.74	2.65	2.52	2.14
T ₂	ST with Thiomethoxam 70 WS@ 5 g / kg +SP with Thiomethoxam 25 WG 0.01%	0.00	1.24	1.71	1.62	1.9	2.13	1.77	2.27	2.42	2.9	2.57	2.86	2.61	2.16
T ₃	ST with Imidacloprid 48 FS@ 5 g /kg+ SP with Azadirachtin@ 5% (NSKE)	0.00	0.00	1.74	1.57	3.13	2.12	2.40	2.26	2.47	2.86	2.56	2.75	2.69	2.21
T ₄	Chlorantraniliprol 8.8% + Thiomethoxam17.5% SC (Soil drenching 50 to 100ml/plant, application after 8 to 10 DAT.)	0.00	1.26	1.74	1.58	1.64	2.09	1.85	2.62	2.65	2.83	2.79	2.61	2.65	2.19
T ₅	Spraying with Imidacloprid 17.8 % SL@ 0.005%	0.00	1.31	1.77	1.72	1.97	2.04	1.94	2.34	2.48	3.13	2.76	2.65	2.75	2.23
T ₆	Spraying with Thiomethoxam 25 W. G. @ 0.01%	0.00	1.27	1.77	1.66	1.83	2.12	1.93	2.63	2.56	3.01	2.92	2.52	2.81	2.25
T ₇	Spraying with Pyriproxyfen 10% EC@0.01%	0.00	1.35	1.79	1.55	1.8	2.12	1.85	2.6	2.61	2.81	3.00	2.81	2.86	2.26
T ₈	Spraying with Azadirachtin@ 5% (NSKE)	0.00	1.24	1.74	1.53	1.95	2.05	1.88	2.25	2.48	3.12	2.65	3.5	3.50	2.32
T ₉	Control (Untreated)	0.00	1.94	1.98	2.04	2.06	2.19	2.24	2.72	3.13	3.25	3.37	3.6	3.60	2.67
	S.E. ±	0.00	0.04	0.05	0.18	0.95	0.52	0.23	0.53	0.45	0.47	0.52	0.45	0.60	

C.D. at 5%	0.00	0.13	0.16	0.54	NS	1.56	0.69	1.60	1.37	1.43	1.59	NS	1.83
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** Figures in parentheses are $\sqrt{x+0.5}$ transformed values. DAT= Days after transplanting. *Mean of three replication.

Table 3. Effect of various treatment integration on leaf curl virus disease incidence in tomato during Rabi, 2017-18 (Cv. Pusa Ruby)

No.	Treatments	Disease incidence (%) days after transplanting*							
		15	30	45	60	75	90	Mean	Reduc. (%)
	Seed treatment (ST) with Imidacloprid 48 FS @ 5 g / kg+ Spraying with (SP) Imidacloprid 17.8 SL @ 0.005%	0.00 (0.00)**	0.00 (0.00)	2.85 (9.71)	3.80 (11.24)	8.57 (17.02)	12.38 (20.60)	5.52 (11.71)	45.82
	ST with Thiomethoxam 70 WS@ 5 g / kg +SP with Thiomethoxam 25 WG 0.01%	0.00 (0.00)	0.95 (5.59)	3.62 (10.96)	6.66 (14.95)	9.52 (17.97)	14.28 (22.20)	7.00 (14.33)	37.50
	ST with Imidacloprid 48 FS@ 5 g /kg+SP with Azadirachtin@ 5% (NSKE)	0.00 (0.00)	2.85 (9.71)	4.71 (12.60)	10.47 (18.87)	12.38 (20.60)	17.14 (24.45)	9.51 (17.24)	24.98
	Chlorantraniliprole8.8%+Thiomethoxam17.5% SC (Soil drenching 50 to 100 ml/ plant, application after 8 to 10 DAT)	0.00 (0.00)	1.90 (7.92)	3.81 (11.25)	9.52 (17.97)	10.47 (18.87)	15.23 (22.97)	8.18 (15.79)	33.34
	Spraying with Imidacloprid 17.8 % SL@ 0.005%	0.00 (0.00)	4.76 (7.92)	5.71 (13.82)	11.42 (19.75)	14.28 (22.20)	16.19 (23.72)	10.47 (17.48)	29.14
	Spraying with Thiomethoxam 25 W. G. @ 0.01%	0.00 (0.00)	5.71 (12.60)	6.66 (14.95)	12.37 (20.59)	15.23 (22.97)	18.09 (25.17)	11.61 (19.25)	20.83
	Spraying with Pyriproxyfen 10% EC@0.01%	0.00 (0.00)	6.66 (13.82)	7.61 (16.01)	13.33 (21.41)	16.19 (23.72)	20.00 (26.56)	12.75 (20.30)	12.47
	Spraying with Azadirachtin@ 5% (NSKE)	0.00 (0.00)	7.62 (14.95)	9.51 (17.97)	14.28 (22.20)	17.14 (24.45)	21.90 (27.90)	14.09 (21.49)	4.15
	Control (Untreated)	0.00 (0.00)	8.57 (16.02)	10.47 (18.87)	15.23 (22.97)	18.09 (22.97)	22.85 (28.55)	15.04 (21.87)	0.00
	S.E. \pm	0.00	1.20 (6.28)	1.94 (8.00)	2.25 (5.76)	1.11 (1.71)	0.84 (5.25)	--	--
	C.D. at 5%	0.00	3.72 (11.12)	5.97 (14.14)	6.73 (10.15)	3.42 (5.13)	2.58 (9.24)	--	--

**Figures in parentheses are angular transform values`*= Average of three replication

Table 4. Effect of various treatment integration on leaf curl virus disease incidence in tomato in Summer, 2018-19 (Cv. Pusa Ruby).

Treat. No.	Treatment details	Disease incidence (%) days after transplanting*							
		15	30	45	60	75	90	Mean	Reduc.(%)
T ₁	Seed treatment (ST) with Imidacloprid 48 FS @ 5 g / kg+ Spraying with (SP) Imidacloprid 17.8 SL @ 0.005%	0.00 (0.00)**	2.85 (9.71)	7.61 (16.01)	10.47 (18.87)	12.38 (20.60)	14.28 (22.20)	7.93 (17.47)	66.67
T ₂	ST with Thiomethoxam 70 WS@ 5 g / kg +SP with Thiomethoxam 25 WG 0.01%	0.00 (0.00)	3.80 (11.24)	8.57 (17.02)	11.42 (19.75)	13.33 (21.41)	15.23 (22.97)	9.71 (16.23)	64.45
T ₃	ST with Imidacloprid 48 FS@ 5 g /kg+SP with Azadirachtin@ 5% (NSKE)	1.90 (7.92)	5.71 (13.82)	12.38 (20.60)	14.28 (22.20)	16.19 (23.72)	17.14 (24.45)	11.26 (18.78)	60.00
T ₄	Chlorantraniliprole 8.8% + Thiomethoxam 17.5 % SC (Soil drenching 50 to 100ml/ plant, application after 8 to 10 DAT)	0.95 (5.59)	4.76 (12.60)	11.42 (19.75)	13.33 (21.41)	17.14 (24.45)	16.19 (23.72)	10.63 (17.92)	62.21

T ₅	Spraying with Imidacloprid 17.8 % SL@ 0.005%	2.85 (9.71)	6.66 (14.55)	13.33 (21.41)	15.23 (22.97)	19.05 (25.87)	22.85 (28.55)	13.32 (20.51)	46.67
T ₆	Spraying with Thiomethoxam 25 W. G. @ 0.01%	2.85 (9.71)	8.57 (17.02)	14.28 (22.20)	16.19 (23.72)	20.00 (26.56)	25.71 (30.46)	14.60 (21.62)	40.00
T ₇	Spraying with Pyriproxyfen 10% EC@0.01%	3.80 (11.24)	9.52 (17.97)	15.23 (22.97)	17.14 (24.45)	22.85 (28.55)	28.56 (32.30)	16.18 (22.91)	33.34
T ₈	Spraying with Azadirachtin@ 5% (NSKE)	4.75 (12.58)	10.47 (18.87)	16.19 (23.27)	18.09 (25.17)	24.76 (29.84)	31.42 (34.09)	17.61 (23.97)	26.67
T ₉	Control (Untreated)	5.71 (13.82)	11.42 (19.75)	17.14 (24.45)	20.00 (26.56)	27.62 (31.70)	42.85 (40.88)	20.79 (26.19)	0.00
	S.E. \pm	0.67 (4.69)	0.74 (4.93)	2.05 (8.23)	1.78 (7.66)	0.96 (5.62)	1.33 (6.62)	--	--
	C.D. at 5%	2.07 (8.27)	2.29 (8.70)	6.32 (14.56)	5.51 (13.57)	2.97 (9.92)	4.10 (11.68)		--

**Figures in parentheses are angular transform values*= Average of three replications

Table 5. Effect of various treatment integration on whitefly population level, disease incidence and yield of tomato in cv. Pusa Ruby

Treat. No.	Treatment	Rabi-2017			Summer-2018		
		Whitefly count mean	Disease incidence mean	Yield (q/ha)	Whitefly count mean	Disease incidence mean	Yield (q/ha)
T ₁	Seed treatment (ST) with Imidacloprid 48 FS @ 5 g / kg+ Spraying with (SP) Imidacloprid 17.8 SL @ 0.005%	1.34	5.52 (11.71)**	347.83	2.14	7.93 (17.47)	306.13
T ₂	ST with Thiomethoxam 70 WS@ 5 g / kg +SP with Thiomethoxam 25 WG 0.01%	1.38	7.00 (14.33)	346.03	2.16	9.71 (16.23)	260.63
T ₃	ST with Imidacloprid 48 FS@ 5 g /kg+SP with Azadirachtin@ 5% (NSKE)	1.44	9.51 (17.24)	256.82	2.21	11.26 (18.78)	175.34
T ₄	Chlorantraniliprole 8.8% + Thiomethoxam 17.5% SC (Soil drenching 50 to 100ml/plant, application after 8 to 10 DAT)	1.42	8.18 (15.79)	328.88	2.19	10.63 (17.92)	287.30
T ₅	Spraying with Imidacloprid 17.8 % SL@ 0.005%	1.45	10.47 (17.48)	254.70	2.23	13.32 (20.51)	151.32
T ₆	Spraying with Thiomethoxam 25 W. G. @ 0.01%	1.47	11.61 (19.25)	247.61	2.25	14.60 (21.61)	137.46
T ₇	Spraying with Pyriproxyfen 10% EC@0.01%	1.54	12.75 (20.30)	235.66	2.26	16.18 (22.91)	124.02
T ₈	Spraying with Azadirachtin@ 5% (NSKE)	1.60	14.09 (21.49)	226.13	2.32	17.61 (23.97)	114.28
T ₉	Control (Untreated)	1.97	15.04 (21.87)	207.40	2.67	20.79 (26.19)	88.88

**Figures in parentheses are angular transform values.

Table 6. Economics of various treatments integrated to tomato for the management of tomato leaf curl virus disease during Rabi, 2017-18

Sr. No.	Treatments	Yield* (q/ha)	Gross income (Rs. /ha)**	Cost of cultivation (Rs. /ha)	Additional income/ha over control	Cost of plant protection (Rs. /ha)(Including labour charges)	Total cost Rs. /ha	Net profit	ICBR
T ₁	Seed treatment (ST) with Imidacloprid 48 FS @ 5 g / kg+ Spraying with (SP) Imidacloprid 17.8 SL @ 0.005%	347.83	1043490	60750	421290	2550	63300	980190	1:15.48
T ₂	ST with Thiomethoxam 70 WS@ 5 g / kg +SP with Thiomethoxam 25 WG 0.01	346.03	1038090	60750	415890	3375	64125	973965	1:15.18
T ₃	ST with Imidacloprid 48 FS@ 5 g /kg+SP with Azadirachtin@ 5% (NSKE)	256.82	770460	60750	148260	1750	62500	707960	1:11.32
T ₄	Chlorantraniliprole 8.8% + Thiomethoxam17.5% SC (Soil drenching 50 to 100ml/plant, application after 8 to 10 DAT)	328.88	986640	60750	364440	10664	71414	915226	1:12.81
T ₅	Spraying with Imidacloprid 17.8 % SL@ 0.005%	254.70	764100	60750	141900	1440	62190	701910	1:11.28
T ₆	Spraying with Thiomethoxam 25 W. G. @ 0.01%	247.61	742830	60750	120630	2275	63025	679805	1:10.78
T ₇	Spraying with Priproxfifen 10% EC@0.01%	235.66	706980	60750	84780	1050	61800	645180	1:10.43
T ₈	Spraying with Azadirachtin@ 5% (NSKE)	226.13	678390	60750	56190	850	61600	616790	1:10.01
T ₉	Control (Untreated)	207.40	622200	60750			60750	561450	1:9.24

*- Mean of three replications, ICBR : Incremental cost : benefit ratio. ** Selling rates of tomato @RS.3000q/ha

Table 7. Economics of various treatments integrated to tomato for the management of tomato leaf curl virus disease during Summer, 2018-19.

Sr. No.	Treatments	Yield (q/ha)	Gross income (Rs. /ha)**	Additional income/ha over control	Cost of cultivation (Rs. /ha)	Cost of plant protection (Rs./ha)(Including labour charges)	Total cost Rs. /ha	Net profit	ICBR
T ₁	Seed treatment (ST) with Imidacloprid 48 FS @ 5 g / kg+ Spraying with (SP) Imidacloprid 17.8 SL @ 0.005%	306.13	1530650	61750	1086250	2550	64300	1466350	1:22.80
T ₂	ST with Thiomethoxam 70 WS@ 5 g / kg +SP with Thiomethoxam 25 WG 0.01%	260.63	1303150	61750	858750	3375	65125	1238025	1:19.00
T ₃	ST with Imidacloprid 48 FS@ 5 g /kg+SP with Azadirachtin@ 5% (NSKE)	175.34	876700	61750	432300	1750	63500	813200	1:12.80
T ₄	Chlorantraniliprole 8.8% + Thiomethoxam17.5% SC (Soil drenching 50 to 100ml/plant, application after 8 to 10 DAT)	287.3	1436500	61750	992100	10664	72414	1364086	1:18.83
T ₅	Spraying with Imidacloprid 17.8 % SL@ 0.005%	151.32	756600	61750	312200	1440	63190	693410	1:10.97
T ₆	Spraying with Thiomethoxam 25 W. G. @ 0.01%	137.46	687300	61750	242900	2275	64025	623275	1:9.73
T ₇	Spraying with Pyriproxyfen 10% EC@0.01%	124.02	620100	61750	175700	1050	62800	557300	1:8.87
T ₈	Spraying with Azadirachtin @ 5% (NSKE)	114.28	571400	61750	127000	850	62600	508800	1:8.12
T ₉	Control (Untreated)	88.88	444400	61750			61750	382650	1:6.19

*-Mean of three replications, ICBR: Incremental cost: benefit ratio ** Selling rates of tomato @RS.5000q/ha